

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Seminars in Cell and Developmental Biology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/semcdb

Crossing boundaries: Interplay between the immune system and oligodendrocyte lineage cells

Leslie Kirby^a, Gonçalo Castelo-Branco^{a,b,*}^a Laboratory of Molecular Neurobiology, Department Medical Biochemistry and Biophysics, Karolinska Institutet, Biomedicum, 17177 Stockholm, Sweden^b Ming Wai Lau Centre for Reparative Medicine, Stockholm Node, Karolinska Institutet, 17177 Stockholm, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Oligodendrocyte
Glia
Astrocyte
Myelin
Neuroimmunology
T-cell
Multiple sclerosis
Aging
Interferon-gamma
Major histocompatibility complex

ABSTRACT

Oligodendrocytes and their progenitors are glial cells in the central nervous system, which have been mainly implicated with the homeostatic roles of axonal myelin ensheathment but serve as targets of the peripheral immune system attack in the context of diseases like multiple sclerosis. This view of oligodendroglia as passive bystanders with no immunological properties was first challenged in the 1980s when it was reported that the cytokine interferon γ could induce the gene expression of the major histocompatibility complexes (MHC) class I and II. While the physiological role of this induction was controversial for decades to follow, recent studies suggest that oligodendroglia survey their environment, respond to a larger array of cues and can indeed exert immunomodulatory functions, which are particularly relevant in the context of neurodegeneration and demyelinating diseases. The alternative functionality of oligodendroglia not only regulates immune cell responses, but also hinders remyelination, and might thereby be key to understanding MS disease pathology and promoting regeneration after immune-mediated demyelination.

1. Introduction

The transition from homeostatic to inflammatory states has several consequences, including cellular recruitment from peripheral and resident sources, immune cell amplification, alteration of resident central nervous system (CNS) cell function and even induced cell death. The overall heterogeneity, spatial organization of CNS tissues and the dynamic changes that occur throughout disease processes both preclinically and chronically, especially in the context of normal biological processes like aging, expand the complexity of the inflammatory functions of resident CNS cells.

While the role of microglia in inflammatory states in the CNS is firmly established, the involvement of non-immune glial cells as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes (OLs) in such processes has only recently come under the spotlight. In neurological disorders, it has become apparent that glial cells can transition to disease-specific cell states, characterized by activation of immune genes, previously thought to be exclusive to immune cells. Prior to immune gene profiling, disease-associated astrocytes were implicated as an impediment to remyelination due to their secretion of hyaluronic acid in demyelinating lesions [1,2]. The synthesis of hyaluronan was linked to the initial observation

of microglial and astrocytic elevated expression of CD44 in EAE and MS [3,4]. Since CD44 is a classical marker of T-cell activation, the early observation of immune and disease states of astrocytes was set in place [5]. More recently, this concept has been further validated by the identification of a neurotoxic astrocytic cell state (A1 astrocytes), induced by activated microglia [6]. A1 astrocytes express complement cascade genes (such as complement component 3, C3), mediate neuronal and OL cell death and are abundant in neurodegenerative diseases, including multiple sclerosis (MS) [6] and Alzheimer's disease [7]. In contrast, single-cell RNA-seq analysis has recently revealed another population of astrocytes expressing high levels of the MAF BZIP Transcription Factor G (MAFG) and low levels of Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-Related Factor 2 (NRF2), that restrain oxidative stress and inflammation, and is abundant in the Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis (EAE) mouse model of MS and in MS patient brain tissue [8]. The role of these alternative astrocytic states in the etiology and progression neurological diseases is still unclear, as they are likely to exhibit many pathological consequences.

OLs produce myelin sheaths that insulate neuronal axons in the CNS, and have been thought to be mainly passive targets of the adaptive immune system attack to myelin in the context of MS. Acquisition of a

* Corresponding author at: Laboratory of Molecular Neurobiology, Department Medical Biochemistry and Biophysics, Karolinska Institutet, Biomedicum, 17177 Stockholm, Sweden

E-mail address: goncalo.castelo-branco@ki.se (G. Castelo-Branco).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semcdb.2020.10.013>

Received 18 June 2020; Received in revised form 12 September 2020; Accepted 26 October 2020

1084-9521/© 2020 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

disease-specific OL state characterized by the expression of immune-related genes could possibly allow a direct cross-talk between OLs and immune cells and therefore modulation of immune responses by OLs. In this review, we will focus on the mechanisms by which OPCs and OLs (referred collectively as oligodendroglia in this review) with an immunological profile (hereafter named iOPCs and iOLs) are induced and the role of iOPCs/iOLs in normal physiology and disease pathology. Recent work with single-cell RNA-seq of the OL lineage in the spinal cord of mice at the peak of EAE revealed transitions of OLG to iOPCs and iOLs [9]. Some of these states were characterized by gene modules associated with interferon response and major histocompatibility complex (MHC) -I and -II genes [9]. IFN γ was shown to be key for the induction of these gene modules in OPCs *in vitro* [9,10], as well as *in vivo*, upon transgenic overexpression of IFN γ by astrocytes, coupled with induction of the cuprizone model of de/remyelination [10]. Furthermore, these studies established a novel role of OPCs in antigen presentation via major histocompatibility complex (MHC) class I and MHC-II *in vivo* [9–11].

2. Induction of iOPCs/iOLs

2.1. Sounding the alarm

The classical pathway needed to harbor an immune response occurs in stages with differential responses at the cellular level defined by innate and adaptive immunity. Sounding the alarm upon recognition of damage or presence of a pathogen serves as the response initiator. For instance, infection with mouse hepatitis coronavirus leads to demyelinating encephalomyelitis, with infected OPCs and MOLs expressing elevated MHC-I, antigen presentation and interferon response genes [12]. Microorganism infection and damage recognition incorporate an additional whole host of receptors and intracellular signaling molecules. The original aberrant signaling cue and the source of the alarm remain unknown in the context of MS. Nevertheless, canonical receptors and intracellular signaling molecules necessary for the initial events of the innate immune response, such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs) [13], have been shown to be expressed in OLs. The first reports that focused on TLR signaling in oligodendrocytes found that TLR2 and TLR3 were homeostatically expressed in primary OLs and astrocytes isolated from corpora callosa and subcortical white matter tissues [14]. TLR2 expression was further confirmed in microglia, astrocytes and oligodendrocytes but not neurons [15]. Intracellular mediators of TLR signaling like TIR-domain-containing adapter-inducing interferon- β (*TRIF*), TIR Domain Containing Adaptor Protein (*TIRAP*) and *MyD88* Innate Immune Signal Transduction Adaptor gene expression have differential expression patterns with the OL lineage. *TRIF* expression was found in OPC populations from control and EAE spinal cord tissue, *TIRAP* was restricted to mature oligodendrocytes regardless of condition, and *MyD88* expression being present across the entire lineage but specifically in EAE conditions [9]. While these observations are preliminary, indicating potential involvement of iOPC/iOL in initial immune activating events, further study is required to determine the functionality of these signaling pathways.

2.2. Cytokines involved in immune transitions to iOPCs/iOLs

2.2.1. IFN γ as an inducer of immune transitions in OPCs/OLs

Innate, adaptive and resident CNS inflammatory cells secrete a broad range of cytokines, numbering over 300 have been identified [16]. The pleiotropic nature of many cytokines, their combinatorial signaling, the contextual differences of varying microenvironments and the distinctive inherent properties of the receptive cell paint a complex picture for understanding neuroinflammation.

Pioneering immunochemistry-based experiments in the 1980's indicated that treatment with interferon gamma (IFN γ) could induce mouse OLs to express MHC-I molecules, involved in antigen presentation, while MHC-I and MHC-II dual expression was restricted to astrocytes [17–21]. Other studies suggested that IFN γ could also induce

MHC-II in O-2A progenitors (bipotent progenitors of astrocytes and oligodendrocytes) but not mature oligodendrocytes [22]. Later studies indicated that mature OLs (MOLs) from the optic nerve could express MHC-II upon co-stimulation of IFN γ and the glucocorticoid dexamethasone [23]. Several MHC-II genes were also observed to be induced by IFN γ alone in rat post-natal OPCs and MOLs, although to a lesser extent in the latter [24].

While *in vitro* experiments clearly indicated that astrocytes and OLs are able to express MHC-I and -II genes upon stimulation with IFN γ , there was controversy whether this was the case *in vivo*. Intrathecal injection of IFN γ in rats led to an induction of MHC-I and -II in astrocytes [25]. While MHC-II positive astrocytes were first detected by chromogenic immunostaining in acute and active chronic MS lesions [26,27], studies with confocal microscopy and immunofluorescence suggested that this was not the case [28,29]. Likewise, OLs were also reported not to express MHC-II molecules in active lesions from MS patients [30,31]. Nevertheless, both astrocytes and OLs exhibited higher expression of MHC-I in active and inactive lesions in MS [28], and immunohistochemical analysis suggested that transcription regulators as RFX5 and CIITA, regulating both MHC-I and MHC-II expression, are weakly/moderately expressed in subsets of hypertrophic astrocytes in active demyelinating lesions [30]. Taken together, early studies, albeit contradictory at times, suggested that IFN γ could be important for transitioning glial cells to an inflammatory state with MHC class I and II presentation as the main features.

2.2.2. Modulation of cell death, survival and differentiation of OPCs/OLs by IFN γ

IFN γ treatment was shown to lead to cell death by apoptosis or necrosis of OL lineage cells [32–36], an outcome not observed in other studies, where IFN γ did not affect cell survival but rather decreased OL differentiation [9,10,19,37]. These apparently disparate results could suggest that factors such as IFN γ concentration, cell culture media composition and/or specific developmental/differentiation stage might play a role in the induction of expression of MHC genes and cellular response of OLs cells upon IFN γ exposure *in vitro*.

In vivo, transgenically driven expression of IFN γ in the OL [38] or astrocyte [35,39] lineages lead to an upregulation of MHC-I (and MHC-II) in the CNS, with severe endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress in OLs and consequent apoptosis. Overexpressed MHC molecules were shown to accumulate in the ER of OLs, generating ER stress [35,40]. Ultimately continued ER stress led to a reduction of developmental myelination, and symptomology consistent with hypomyelination [35]. Similarly to IFN γ delivery to the developing CNS, overexpression of the MHC-I molecule H-2K in OLs (under the myelin basic protein promoter) also led to a hypomyelination phenotype, driven by a delay in developmental myelination and/or oligodendrocyte cell death [41,42]. Nevertheless, overexpression of another MHC-I molecule, H-2L under the proteolipid protein (*Ptp*) promoter, did not present a dysfunction in myelination [43]. Beta 2 microglobulin (*B2m*), which forms a complex with the heavy chain MHC-I molecule and the peptide antigen, is only weakly associated with H-2L, which could explain the differences in phenotype between these mice strains [43].

While induction of IFN γ expression during adulthood did not lead to OL cell death or defects in myelination [35], astrocyte-driven delivery of IFN γ in the context of EAE and cuprizone induced-demyelination led to impaired remyelination, consistent with the phenotype observed upon IFN γ delivery in the developing CNS [44]. The discrepancy of data might be related with the differential demands on protein synthesis between actively myelinating oligodendrocytes and MOLs [35]. IFN γ might induce cell death to newly formed oligodendrocytes derived from OPCs in MS lesions while regulating other processes in the existing MOLs. Paradoxically, one of these processes might be survival [45]. IFN γ can have a protective effect if delivered to the CNS prior to EAE onset, by inducing an integrated stress response, through limited endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, phosphorylation of the eukaryotic translation

initiation factor 2 (eIF2 α), reduction of protein synthesis and induction of protective genes [46]. Overall, the strong effect of IFN γ signaling in OPC and OLs is highly variable depending on the expression system, model system and concentration, which is further complicated by OPC/OL heterogeneity and simultaneously occurring direct and indirect mechanisms.

2.2.3. Additional cues for immune transitions to iOPCs/iOLs

While IFN γ is the most well-documented cytokine known to influence OLs and other glia, other cytokines like IL17 and TNF α have been reported to modulate OL function [47,48]. Deletion of NF- κ B activator 1 (Act1), which is downstream of interleukin 17 (IL-17), specifically in OPCs but not in MOLs, led to a robust reduction of EAE severity [49]. IL17 signaling through Act1 led to downstream activation of caspase signaling and induced cell death of OPCs [49]. In addition, IL17-stimulated OPCs interact with astrocytes through Notch signaling, which initiates gene expression of several key chemokines and immunomodulatory molecules [48]. However, IL17 seemingly does not activate the expression of genes involved in antigen presentation pathways within the OLs even though it robustly inhibits differentiation similarly to IFN γ [10].

While IFN γ and IL17 can singularly impact OL immune transitions, TNF α has been classified as more of a fine-tuning or synergizing cytokine. Co-treatment of TNF α with IFN γ and/or IL17 to OPC cultures led to greater percentages of cell death and lower rates of differentiation when compared to either cytokine treatment alone [50,51]. However, the observed apoptotic effect of IL17 on OPCs was also reported to be independent of TNF α induced signaling [49]. Chemokine, cytokine and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) gene expression in primary OPCs was predominantly driven by recombinant TNF α treatment whether treated in isolation or in combination with IL17 [49]. It is important to recognize the differential signaling effects these cytokines have in regards to dose, the functional changes induced and the synergistic and combinatorial effect of multiple cytokines. Moreover, the wide array of cytokines relevant in immune-mediated CNS diseases necessitates further investigation.

3. Function and regulation of iOPCs/iOLs

3.1. Chemoattraction of immune cells by iOPC/iOLs

IFN γ is not expressed by the OL lineage [52,53], not even in the context of EAE [9]. However, many other immunomodulatory molecules, including cytokines and chemokines, have been shown to be expressed by OLs (reviewed by [54]). For instance, the OL lineage not only activates MHC-I and -II but also starts expressing cytokines, such as CXCL10, CCL2, CCL3, CCL5, upon exposure to IFN γ [45]. Activated OPCs in the cuprizone model of demyelination/remyelination express CCL2 and interleukin-1 β [55]. Both these chemokines activate OPC migration, furthermore CCL2 is expressed in 3–5% of OPCs in active regions of MS plaques [55]. Bacterial infection of oligodendrocytes with *Borrelia burgdorferi* causes their expression of CCL2, IL-8 and IL-6 [56], providing greater evidence of OL lineage chemokine and cytokine expression beyond autoimmune driven disease. IL17 signaling through Act1 and NOTCH stimulates OPC to express CXCL1, CCL7 and S100a9 [48]. Taking this entire repertoire of signaling ligands together OPCs/OLs can potentially recruit a whole host of immune cells to inflammatory niches in the CNS.

On the innate arm of the immune system, OPCs/OLs may have a role in initial events important for cellular recruitment, for instance, neutrophil recruitment through CXCL1/CXCR2 interaction. Intracerebral injection of mouse hepatitis virus establishes prominent neutrophil infiltration into the brain parenchyma within three days of infection [57]. Furthermore, MOL cell death and demyelination ensues by sustained transgenic expression of CXCL1 [58]. While the native cellular source of CXCL1 following mouse hepatitis virus infection remains

unclear, transgenic expression of N51/KC (alternative neutrophil specific ligand) driven by the MBP promoter was sufficient in establishing neutrophil recruitment to perivascular, meningeal and parenchymal compartments [59]. The potential of OPC/OL driven neutrophil recruitment to the CNS is compelling and warrants further investigation to provide clarity regarding the resident CNS cellular involvement in inflammatory cell recruitment processes. Peripheral monocytes and macrophage recruitment by OPCs/OLs is also probable since there are several lines of evidence for their production of CCL2 and CCL7, two ligands that bind the CCR2 receptor [60,61]. Not only are OPCs responsible for cytokine secretion, they are also receptive to innate cytokine signaling; for example, IL-6 and IL-1 β reduce the proliferative capacity of NG2 glia shortly after systemic injection of LPS [62]. It is important to note that while OPCs/OLs may have a role in the cellular recruitment of innate immune cells, microglia are well defined at performing these functions. Interestingly, fine-tuning of microglia signals or maintenance of their homeostatic state could be an alternative influence that OPCs/OLs may have [63] (reviewed in [64]).

Moving from the innate to the adaptive arm of cellular recruitment and the influences OPC/OLs have on encouraging cellular infiltration is more challenging due to the establishment of the acute immune response by innate cells and the inherent complexity that ensues. While OPC/OL role as a primary recruiter of adaptive cells to the CNS is unknown, the specific compartment and microenvironment migration within the CNS (ie parenchyma versus meninges/perivascular regions) may be a more prominent role of iOPCs/iOLs. As stated, above OPCs/OLs express and are reactive to CCL2, CXCL10, CCL3, CCL5 and S100a9 ligands [65–67] important for establishing effector/memory T-cell and B-cell populations along with NK cells. Recently OPCs were shown to exhibit perivascular clustering in MS and lysolecithin models of demyelination. Importantly OPCs disrupt the blood-brain barrier (BBB) making it more permeable to infiltrating CD3⁺ lymphocytes [68].

3.2. Immune cell activation by iOPCs/iOLs

The increased expression of the inflammatory cytokines IFN γ , IL17 and TNF α requires activation of T-cell and/or B-cell lymphocyte populations by antigen presentation. Lymphocyte activation relies on physical engagement and interaction of antigen-loaded MHC molecules and the specific T-cell receptor (TCR) which has been termed signal I. In addition to the mere physical docking of MHC with its cognate TCR, other signaling molecules interact through transmembrane ligand-receptor pairing and secreted ligand-receptor activation forming the immunological synapse between cells and employing further activating signaling termed signal II and signal III [69–72]. Clonal expansion and epitope spreading of T-cells and B-cells are characterizing attributes of MS disease pathology, however, the precise mechanism for the establishment of these properties remains unknown. Antigen presentation can involve phagocytosis, and OPCs were shown to be capable of phagocytosing myelin [9]. Moreover, co-culture of IFN γ and MOG^{35–55} peptide pre-treated OPCs with CD4⁺ memory T-cells expressing the TCR for myelin oligodendrocyte protein (MOG^{35–55}) led to CD4⁺ cellular activation via promotion of survival, proliferation and cytokine production [9]. The cross-talk between OPCs and T-cells was also shown in other MS-related disease models. Adoptive transfer of T-cells in mice undergoing cuprizone treatment prevented remyelination by reducing the number of OPCs [10].

OPCs were also shown to be able to activate CD8⁺ T-cells, with antigen cross-presentation leading to increased survival, proliferation and cytokine production by the latter, and ultimately resulting in OPC cell death [10]. The propensity of iOPCs to essentially initiate their own cell death through CD8⁺ T-cell activation was observed not only *in vitro*, but also *in vivo* upon adoptive transfer of T-cells expressing the MOG^{35–55} peptide specific TCR or the MOG^{97–114} peptide specific TCR into cuprizone-fed mice [10]. Antigen presentation by OPCs was also shown to require the phagocytic receptor Low-density lipoprotein receptor-

related protein 1 (LRP1) [73]. Conditional knock-out of LRP1 in the OL lineage (under the *Olig1* promoter) led to impaired MHC-I mediated cross-presentation in the context of cuprizone and EAE [73]. MHC-I, -II and immunoproteasome genes were downregulated in LRP1^{-/-} OPCs at the peak of EAE [73]. This ultimately led to a protective effect on the EAE symptomatology, consistent with enhanced remyelination observed in the cuprizone model upon LRP1^{-/-} OPCs [73].

Preventing cell death of OLs in the EAE mouse model has been shown to confer protection [74,75]. While OL cell death has been thought to be a consequence of prior peripheral immune activation, cuprizone induced OL cell death has also been recently shown to trigger leukocyte influx into the CNS after a peripheral innate immune boost and pertussis mediated BBB breakdown [76,77]. However, alternative experimental paradigms using diphtheria toxin driven MOL cell death did not confer adaptive immune cell infiltration, even when autoimmune conditions were encouraged experimentally [78]. Nevertheless, it is possible that the initial trigger of MS resides in the abnormal induction of iOPCs/iOL rather than a malfunctioning peripheral immune system, the currently prevalent view in the field.

3.3. Alternative functions of iOPC/iOLs

While iOPCs/iOLs might be involved in a feedback loop that ultimately leads to their cell death, a subset of them might be protected by the induction of genes involved in cell survival, and thus being able to exert alternative immunomodulatory and non-immunomodulatory functions. *Serpina3n*, encoding for a protein involved in protection from T or NK cells, and other *Serpins*, are increased in specific iOPCs and iMOLs subpopulations [9]. The glucocorticoid dexamethasone induced another set of genes such as *Plin4*, present in MOL populations not expressing MHC-II [9]. Extracellular matrix organization could be an important alternative function with immune-modulatory influences. Single-cell transcriptomics provide greater evidence for the role of iOPCs/iMOLs in processes that remodel ECM. A host of matrix metalloproteins of the MMP and ADAM families are implemented and linked to OPC/OL populations in EAE and control conditions and IFN γ stimulated OPCs *in vitro* [9]. Experimentally MMP-9 deletion impairs remyelination after lysolecithin [79]. MMP-12 was found to be secreted by OLs and important for process extension [80]. ADAM17, a key modulator of OL development, is heightened in iMOL populations resulting from EAE [9,81]. Therefore, it is likely that, in addition to the inflammatory functioning of iOPCs/iMOLs, differential state changes resulting from inflammatory cues could confer an even greater repertoire of functions resulting in broader disease implications.

3.4. Regulatory control of iOPCs/iOLs

OPCs/OLs can react to regulatory stimulus derived from regulatory T-cells (T-regs) and B-cells (B-regs), especially in the context of a dampened immune function of OLs in the effort to promote repair. Cellular Communication Network Factor 3 (CCN3) produced by T-regs promoted remyelination of oligodendrocytes following lysolecithin demyelination by promoting differentiation [82]. In addition, the adoptive transfer of B-regs in EAE mice altered the inflammatory milieu allowing for remyelination processes to occur [83]. It remains unclear whether T-regs and B-regs can modulate iOPC/iOL function. Recently, NG2 glia were found to have a regulatory function in innate immunity via suppression of microglial CX3CR1 signaling through TGF- β 2/TGFRB2 signaling, as ablation of NG2 glia increased IL-1 β production in brain tissue following peripheral injection of LPS [63]. One important factor that needs further elucidation is the precise signaling mechanism that are promoting these regulatory repair strategies and whether they are operational in iOPCs/iOLs. When thinking of remyelination, we need to have better understanding of the overall heterogeneity of iOPC/iOLs and the consequences of their immune function. Specifically, do the immune primed iOPCs/iOLs retain their plasticity and ability to revert

back to its differentiating myelinating role? Considerations of the dynamic changes and temporal changes that occur throughout disease processes and CNS inflammation are important for determining of the overall influence and importance of iOPCs/iOLs.

4. iOPCs/iOLs in human disease

4.1. iOPCs/iOLs in MS patients

As mentioned previously, iOPCs and iOLs were identified in lesions in the spinal cord of the EAE mouse model of MS and other models of demyelination [9,10]. Single nuclei RNA-Seq has allowed for the interrogation of the presence of iOPCs and iOLs in human frozen CNS samples, both in cortical white matter tissue from 5 individuals with no neurological conditions and normal-appearing white matter and lesions from 4 individuals with progressive MS [84]. Induction of immune genes in OLs was observed in both healthy individuals and MS patients, with an enrichment in the latter. Interestingly, in contrast to EAE, iOPCs were not identified, while iOLs presented characteristics of intermediated OLs. It is unclear whether these differences are related to the stage of disease (peak disease in EAE, post-mortem in MS) or region (spinal cord in EAE, brain in MS), further raising the question of whether iOPCs and iOLs have different functions. The differential functionality of iOPCs and iOLs could also imply species-specific differences in the function of immunocompetent OL lineage cells. While preliminary, the presence of immune gene expression in healthy control human CNS tissue and control mouse OPCs/OLs is suggestive that oligodendrocyte lineage cells are primed and receptive to an immune stimulus at steady state, especially when considering the gene involved in TLR signaling as mentioned above [9,84].

Analysis of cortical gray matter and subcortical white matter showed increased expression of MHC genes, *B2M* and *HLA-C*, alongside other genes suggesting a stressed oligodendrocyte signature [85]. Interestingly, in this study the myelin transcripts, *MBP* and *PLP1* were observed in phagocytizing microglial cells. In cultured human and mouse microglial cells, these transcripts appear to be present in perinuclear and nuclear compartments [85]. It is unclear what would be the function and physiological relevance of the translocation of such exogenous transcripts to the nucleus of microglia. Nevertheless, OLs expressing the immunoproteasome component PSMB8 [10] and MHC-II [9] at the protein level were observed in MS lesions, suggesting that iOPCs/iOLs might exert immunomodulatory functions in MS.

4.2. iOPCs/iOLs in other neurodegenerative disorders

While there has been a major focus on iOPCs/iOLs involvement in MS due to the clear pathological coupling of demyelination and neuroinflammation, there remains a whole host of CNS diseases and disorders in which iOPCs/iOLs could play a functional role. Injury and neuroinflammatory diseases, including but not limited to neuromyelitis optica, viral encephalitis, autoimmune polyneuropathies and diseases driven by autoantibodies, especially with antigen specificity to myelin, warrants further investigation into the role of iOPCs/iOLs. The influence of iOPCs/iOLs on other CNS diseases that are not primarily driven by neuroinflammation but are influenced by it, such as schizophrenia, autism spectrum disorders, Parkinson's disease and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, would also be of interest for future studies. Depending on the clinical features of the disease and the region of the CNS impacted, diverse roles of iOPCs/iOLs are likely. For example, ablation of NG2 glia was found to promote neuroinflammation and loss of dopaminergic neurons from the substantia nigra in a mouse model of Parkinson's disease, suggesting that these cells are responsible for the suppression of innate immune signaling [63].

It has been recently reported that a subpopulation of reactive OLs expressing *Serpina3n*, complement component *C4b* and the MHC class I, *H2-d1* exists in a mouse model of Alzheimer disease (5XFAD) [86]. The

induction of *C4b* and *Serpina3n* is partially dependent on Trem2 [86], which plays an important role in microglia function. Increased *C4b* was also observed in 5XFAD OPCs [86]. Since these genes are also upregulated in iOPCs and iOLs in EAE [9], similar mechanisms might regulate the induction of immunological properties in OPCs in both mouse models of Alzheimer's disease and MS.

Overall, the role of iOPC/iOLs in CNS diseases and disorders is largely unknown as to whether their inflammatory function is prominent or merely limited to a fine-tuning effect, further elucidation remains critical for our understanding of neuroinflammation and therapeutic development.

4.3. iOPCs/iOLs in aging

Aging might be another factor that can induce immunological properties in oligodendrocyte lineage cells. scRNA-Seq profiling of young (2–3 months) and aging (21–23 months) brains revealed increased expression of the MHC-I genes, *B2m*, *H2-D1* and *H2-K1*, but also of *C4b* in OPCs and/or OLs, with humoral immune response and regulation of phagocytosis as pathways increased specifically in OLs [87]. Comparison of juvenile (P12) and aged (P310) mouse OPCs also showed increased expression in the latter population of genes involved in antigen processing and presentation, response to IFN γ and defense response [88]. This putative aging effect of transitioning to alternative states is not restricted to OL lineage cells. CD8⁺ T-cells have been shown to infiltrate the subventricular zone of aged mice (28–29 months), where they reside in the proximity of neural stem cells and reduce their proliferation [89]. Interestingly OPCs and OLs in the aging SVZ also present upregulation of *C4b* and MHC I genes (*B2m*, *H2-d1*), with OLs specifically increasing expression of *Serpina3n* [89]. Gene Set Enrichment Analysis of old SVZ OPCs and OLs, in comparison to young counterparts, showed increased expression of genes involved in IFN γ and α response and IL6/JAK/STAT3 signaling in these populations, with inflammatory response and IL2/STAT5 signaling specifically in aged OLs. Aged OLs also exhibit increased *Bst2* expression, which is a marker NSCs IFN γ response in the aged SVZ [89]. Interestingly, *Bst2* is also strongly induced in iOPCs and iOLs in EAE [9].

As in the aged SVZ [89], T-cells, entering the CNS through a compromised BBB, might be one of the sources of inflammatory activating molecules in MS. Recent single-cell transcriptomics studies have also highlighted subtypes of immune cell types that are present in EAE/MS lesions at the peak or chronic stages of the disease [90–92]. It is possible that these cells induce iOPC/iOLs, which would then contribute to the reactivation, boosting or maintenance of an immune response (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, the limited number of iOPCs/iOLs at the peak of EAE [9] instead suggests a role in other stages of the disease. A hypothesis would be that iOPC/iOLs are induced in early disease stages in response to local inflammation driven by OL cell death or other triggers such as viral infection. iOPCs/iOLs would then actively promote the

recruitment of peripheral immune cells via recruitment and antigen presentation, kickstarting a cascade that would ultimately lead to the autoimmune attack on myelin. Further studies might elucidate if iOPCs/iOLs are involved in a putative “inside-out” or “outside-in” mechanism of EAE and MS.

5. Conclusions

Understanding neuroinflammation introduces the requirement of overcoming many complex obstacles. One primary obstacle is the heterogeneous nature of the many cell types involved during homeostasis, both at the transcriptomic/proteomic levels and the spatial organization of compartment localization. Further convolution is created at the juxtaposition of differential disease states, both neuroinflammatory and neurodegenerative while considering the dynamic characteristics of cellular plasticity, turnover, mobility and the interactive nature inherent to most of the cell types involved in these pathological and reparative processes.

While glia cells have been thought to play a limited role in neurodegenerative diseases, in the past few years they have started to take front stage. Nevertheless, it is still unclear whether they are actively involved in the etiology, maintenance, propagation, reactivation of these disorders, or if their involvement is merely bystander. Interestingly, many of the transcriptional programs observed in iOPCs/iOLs have been associated with susceptibility genes in MS [93]. Additional MS susceptibility genes in non-MHC loci were also found to be expressed in iOPCs and iMOLs, but surprisingly also in non-diseased OPCs [9]. In addition, regulatory regions contain outside variants associated with MS risk have been recently shown also to be involved in the dysfunction of transcriptional elongation during OL maturation and to be dysregulated in OLs in MS patients [94]. Therefore, MS susceptibility might be reflected in abnormal function not only of immune cells, but also OL lineage cells.

While model organisms such as rodents have allowed the unveiling of putative novel functions of glia, the lack of appropriate human *in vitro* models is a major hindrance to furthering the evaluation of the relevance of the immunomodulatory functions of glia. Recent studies have confirmed the capacity of human oligodendroglia derived from pluripotent cells to transition to immune states [95,96]. While organoids can mimic several aspects of human neural development, currently, they do not allow for the recapitulation of the complex interactions occurring in diseased niches in the intact CNS. Humanized mice, where human glia has replaced the endogenous mouse glia [97], might allow for the investigation of their function in a physiological environment. New technologies such as single nuclei transcriptomics have uncovered new properties of glia in post-mortem archived disease tissues [84,85]. However, the application of archival material poses several challenges, of which the most challenging might be the low depth of detection when compared with single-cell technologies using biopsies, which pose

Fig. 1. The choices of OPCs in the context of neuroinflammation: participate in remyelination or cross the boundary and become immune OPCs (iOPCs). Oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPCs) differentiate into myelin-producing oligodendrocytes during normal development and in homeostasis and regeneration in adulthood (path to the left). In the context of neuroinflammation, direct contact of OPCs with immune cells such as T-cells, and/or exposure to cytokines as IFN- γ , released by immune cells, leads to a transition to an iOPC state. iOPCs can present antigens to CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T-cells, leading to their activation (increased survival, proliferation and cytokine production). This can lead to a negative feedback loop with the induction of iOPC cell death, or in case of survival, to alternative immune or non-immune functions of iOPCs.

additional ethical and logistic challenges. Nevertheless, the integration with other modalities as single-nuclei epigenomics [98], single-cell proteomics and spatial transcriptomic technologies will continue to provide novel insights on the role of glia in neurodegenerative disorders.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Amagoia Agirre for designing the illustration in Fig. 1. Leslie Kirby was supported by the European Committee for Treatment and Research in Multiple Sclerosis (ECTRIMS). Gonçalo Castelo-Branco was supported by the Swedish Research Council (grant 2015–03558 and 2019–01360), the European Union (FP7/Marie Curie Integration Grant EPIOPC, Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme/European Research Council Consolidator Grant EPISCOPE, grant agreement number 681893), the Swedish Brain Foundation (FO2017–0075), the Ming Wai Lau Centre for Reproductive Medicine, the Swedish Cancer Society (Cancerfonden; 19 0394 Pj 02H), Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation (grant 2019–0107), the Swedish Society for Medical Research (SSMF, grant JUB2019) and Karolinska Institutet.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

References

- [1] M. Bugiani, N. Postma, E. Polder, N. Dieleman, P.G. Scheffer, F.J. Sim, M.S. van der Knaap, I. Boor, Hyaluronan accumulation and arrested oligodendrocyte progenitor maturation in vanishing white matter disease, *Brain* 136 (2013) 209–222.
- [2] S.A. Back, T.M.F. Tuohy, H. Chen, N. Wallingford, A. Craig, J. Struve, N.L. Luo, F. Banine, Y. Liu, A. Chang, B.D. Trapp, B.F. Bebo., M.S. Rao, L.S. Sherman, Hyaluronan accumulates in demyelinated lesions and inhibits oligodendrocyte progenitor maturation, *Nat. Med.* 11 (2005) 966–972.
- [3] N. Girgah, M. Letarte, L.E. Becker, T.F. Cruz, E. Theriault, M.A. Moscarello, Localization of the CD44 glycoprotein to fibrous astrocytes in normal white matter and to reactive astrocytes in active lesions in multiple sclerosis, *J. Neuropathol. Exp. Neurol.* 50 (1991) 779–792.
- [4] H. Haegel, C. Tolg, M. Hofmann, R. Ceredig, Activated mouse astrocytes and T cells express similar CD44 variants. Role of CD44 in astrocyte/T cell binding, *J. Cell Biol.* 122 (1993) 1067–1077.
- [5] S.T. Pals, G. Koopman, K.H. Heider, A. Griffioen, G.R. Adolf, F. Van den Berg, H. Ponta, P. Herrlich, E. Horst, CD44 splice variants: expression during lymphocyte activation and tumor progression, *Behring Inst. Mitt.* (1993) 273–277.
- [6] S.A. Liddelow, K.A. Guttenplan, L.E. Clarke, F.C. Bennett, C.J. Bohlen, L. Schirmer, M.L. Bennett, A.E. Münch, W.S. Chung, T.C. Peterson, D.K. Wilton, A. Frouin, B. A. Napier, N. Panicker, M. Kumar, M.S. Buckwalter, D.H. Rowitch, V.L. Dawson, T. M. Dawson, B. Stevens, B.A. Barres, Neurotoxic reactive astrocytes are induced by activated microglia, *Nature* 541 (2017) 481–487.
- [7] N. Habib, C. McCabe, S. Medina, M. Varshavsky, D. Kitsberg, R. Dvir-Szternfeld, G. Green, D. Dionne, L. Nguyen, J.L. Marshall, F. Chen, F. Zhang, T. Kaplan, A. Regev, M. Schwartz, Disease-associated astrocytes in Alzheimer's disease and aging, *Nat. Neurosci.* 23 (2020) 701–706.
- [8] M.A. Wheeler, I.C. Clark, E.C. Tjon, Z. Li, S.E.J. Zandee, C.P. Couturier, B. R. Watson, G. Scalisi, S. Alkwa, V. Rothhammer, A. Rotem, J.A. Heyman, S. Thaploo, L.M. Sanmarco, J. Ragoussi, D.A. Weitz, K. Petrecca, J.R. Moffitt, B. Becher, J.P. Antel, A. Prat, F.J. Quintana, MAFG-driven astrocytes promote CNS inflammation, *Nature* 578 (2020) 593–599.
- [9] A.M. Falcão, D. van Bruggen, S. Marques, M. Meijer, S. Jäkel, E. Agirre, n Samudiyata, E.M. Floriddia, D.P. Vanichkina, C. Ffrench-Constant, A. Williams, A. O. Guerreiro-Cacais, G. Castelo-Branco, Disease-specific oligodendrocyte lineage cells arise in multiple sclerosis, *Nat. Med.* 24 (2018) 1837–1844.
- [10] L. Kirby, J. Jin, J.G. Cardona, M.D. Smith, K.A. Martin, J. Wang, H. Strasburger, L. Herbst, M. Alexis, J. Karnell, T. Davidson, R. Dutta, J. Goverman, D. Bergles, P. A. Calabresi, Oligodendrocyte precursor cells present antigen and are cytotoxic targets in inflammatory demyelination, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 3887.
- [11] Q. Ji, L. Castelli, J.M. Goverman, MHC class I-restricted myelin epitopes are cross-presented by Tip-DCs that promote determinant spreading to CD8(+) T cells, *Nat. Immunol.* 14 (2013) 254–261.
- [12] R. Pan, Q. Zhang, S.M. Anthony, Y. Zhou, X. Zou, M. Cassell, S. Perlman, Oligodendrocytes that survive acute coronavirus infection induce prolonged inflammatory responses in the CNS, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 117 (2020) 15902–15910.
- [13] B.A. Beutler, TLRs and innate immunity, *Blood* 113 (2009) 1399–1407.
- [14] M. Bsibsi, R. Ravid, D. Gveric, J.M. van Noort, Broad expression of Toll-like receptors in the human central nervous system, *J. Neuropathol. Exp. Neurol.* 61 (2002) 1013–1021.
- [15] S. Lehnardt, P. Henneke, E. Lien, D.L. Kasper, J.J. Volpe, I. Bechmann, R. Nitsch, J. R. Weber, D.T. Golenbock, T. Vartanian, A mechanism for neurodegeneration induced by group B streptococci through activation of the TLR2/MyD88 pathway in microglia, *J. Immunol.* 177 (2006) 583–592.
- [16] B. Becher, S. Spath, J. Goverman, Cytokine networks in neuroinflammation, *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 17 (2017) 49–59.
- [17] A. Fontana, W. Fierz, H. Wekerle, Astrocytes present myelin basic protein to encephalitogenic T-cell lines, *Nature* 307 (1984) 273–276.
- [18] A. Suzumura, D.H. Silberberg, R.P. Lisak, The expression of MHC antigens on oligodendrocytes: induction of polymorphic H-2 expression by lymphokines, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 11 (1986) 179–190.
- [19] A.M. Turnley, J.F. Miller, P.F. Bartlett, Regulation of MHC molecules on MBP positive oligodendrocytes in mice by IFN-gamma and TNF-alpha, *Neurosci. Lett.* 123 (1991) 45–48.
- [20] H. Wekerle, C. Linington, H. Lassmann, R. Meyermann, Cellular immune reactivity within the CNS, *Trends Neurosci.* 9 (1986) 271–277.
- [21] G.H. Wong, P.F. Bartlett, I. Clark-Lewis, F. Battye, J.W. Schrader, Inducible expression of H-2 and Ia antigens on brain cells, *Nature* 310 (1984) 688–691.
- [22] V.L. Calder, G. Wolswijk, M. Noble, The differentiation of O-2A progenitor cells into oligodendrocytes is associated with a loss of inducibility of Ia antigens, *Eur. J. Immunol.* 18 (1988) 1195–1201.
- [23] K. Bergsteindottir, A. Brennan, K.R. Jessen, R. Mirsky, In the presence of dexamethasone, gamma interferon induces rat oligodendrocytes to express major histocompatibility complex class II molecules, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 89 (1992) 9054–9058.
- [24] T. Itoh, M. Horiuchi, A. Itoh, Interferon-triggered transcriptional cascades in the oligodendroglial lineage: a comparison of induction of MHC class II antigen between oligodendroglial progenitor cells and mature oligodendrocytes, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 212 (2009) 53–64.
- [25] K. Vass, H. Lassmann, Intrathecal application of interferon gamma. Progressive appearance of MHC antigens within the rat nervous system, *Am. J. Pathol.* 137 (1990) 789–800.
- [26] U. Traugott, Multiple sclerosis: relevance of class I and class II MHC-expressing cells to lesion development, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 16 (1987) 283–302.
- [27] U. Traugott, L.C. Scheinberg, C.S. Raine, On the presence of Ia-positive endothelial cells and astrocytes in multiple sclerosis lesions and its relevance to antigen presentation, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 8 (1985) 1–14.
- [28] R. Hoftberger, F. Aboul-Enein, W. Brueck, C. Lucchinetti, M. Rodriguez, M. Schmidbauer, K. Jellinger, H. Lassmann, Expression of major histocompatibility complex class I molecules on the different cell types in multiple sclerosis lesions, *Brain Pathol.* 14 (2004) 43–50.
- [29] L. Bo, S. Mork, P.A. Kong, H. Nyland, C.A. Pardo, B.D. Trapp, Detection of MHC class II-antigens on macrophages and microglia, but not on astrocytes and endothelia in active multiple sclerosis lesions, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 51 (1994) 135–146.
- [30] S.J. Gobin, L. Montagne, M. Van Zutphen, P. Van Der Valk, P.J. Van Den Elsen, C. J. De Groot, Upregulation of transcription factors controlling MHC expression in multiple sclerosis lesions, *Glia* 36 (2001) 68–77.
- [31] S.C. Lee, C.S. Raine, Multiple sclerosis: oligodendrocytes in active lesions do not express class II major histocompatibility complex molecules, *J. Neuroimmunol.* 25 (1989) 261–266.
- [32] M. Horiuchi, A. Itoh, D. Pleasure, T. Itoh, MEK-ERK signaling is involved in interferon-gamma-induced death of oligodendroglial progenitor cells, *J. Biol. Chem.* 281 (2006) 20095–20106.
- [33] M. Horiuchi, A. Itoh, D. Pleasure, K. Ozato, T. Itoh, Cooperative contributions of interferon regulatory factor 1 (IRF1) and IRF8 to interferon-gamma-mediated cytotoxic effects on oligodendroglial progenitor cells, *J. Neuroinflamm.* 8 (2011) 8.
- [34] K.D. Baerwald, B. Popko, Developing and mature oligodendrocytes respond differently to the immune cytokine interferon-gamma, *J. Neurosci. Res.* 52 (1998) 230–239.
- [35] W. Lin, H.P. Harding, D. Ron, B. Popko, Endoplasmic reticulum stress modulates the response of myelinating oligodendrocytes to the immune cytokine interferon-gamma, *J. Cell Biol.* 169 (2005) 603–612.
- [36] T. Vartanian, Y. Li, M. Zhao, K. Stefansson, Interferon-gamma-induced oligodendrocyte cell death: implications for the pathogenesis of multiple sclerosis, *Mol. Med.* 1 (1995) 732–743.
- [37] L.J. Chew, W.C. King, A. Kennedy, V. Gallo, Interferon-gamma inhibits cell cycle exit in differentiating oligodendrocyte progenitor cells, *Glia* 52 (2005) 127–143.
- [38] J.G. Corbin, D. Kelly, E.M. Rath, K.D. Baerwald, K. Suzuki, B. Popko, Targeted CNS expression of interferon-gamma in transgenic mice leads to hypomyelination, reactive gliosis, and abnormal cerebellar development, *Mol. Cell Neurosci.* 7 (1996) 354–370.
- [39] F.M. LaFerla, M.C. Sugarman, T.E. Lane, M.A. Leissring, Regional hypomyelination and dysplasia in transgenic mice with astrocyte-directed expression of interferon-gamma, *J. Mol. Neurosci.* 15 (2000) 45–59.
- [40] K.D. Baerwald, J.G. Corbin, B. Popko, Major histocompatibility complex heavy chain accumulation in the endoplasmic reticulum of oligodendrocytes results in myelin abnormalities, *J. Neurosci. Res.* 59 (2000) 160–169.
- [41] C. Power, P.A. Kong, B.D. Trapp, Major histocompatibility complex class I expression in oligodendrocytes induces hypomyelination in transgenic mice, *J. Neurosci. Res.* 44 (1996) 165–173.
- [42] A.M. Turnley, G. Morahan, H. Okano, O. Bernard, K. Mikoshiba, J. Allison, P. F. Bartlett, J.F. Miller, Dysmyelination in transgenic mice resulting from expression of class I histocompatibility molecules in oligodendrocytes, *Nature* 353 (1991) 566–569.
- [43] B. Fuss, F.S. Afshari, R.J. Colello, W.B. Macklin, Normal CNS myelination in transgenic mice overexpressing MHC class I H-2L(d) in oligodendrocytes, *Mol. Cell Neurosci.* 18 (2001) 221–234.

- [44] W. Lin, A. Kemper, J.L. Dupree, H.P. Harding, D. Ron, B. Popko, Interferon-gamma inhibits central nervous system remyelination through a process modulated by endoplasmic reticulum stress, *Brain* 129 (2006) 1306–1318.
- [45] R. Balabanov, K. Strand, R. Goswami, E. McMahon, W. Begolka, S.D. Miller, B. Popko, Interferon-gamma-oligodendrocyte interactions in the regulation of experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis, *J. Neurosci.* 27 (2007) 2013–2024.
- [46] W. Lin, S.L. Bailely, H. Ho, H.P. Harding, D. Ron, S.D. Miller, B. Popko, The integrated stress response prevents demyelination by protecting oligodendrocytes against immune-mediated damage, *J. Clin. Invest.* 117 (2007) 448–456.
- [47] K.D. Lariosa-Willingham, E.S. Rosler, J.S. Tung, J.C. Dugas, T.L. Collins, D. Leonoudakis, Development of a high throughput drug screening assay to identify compounds that protect oligodendrocyte viability and differentiation under inflammatory conditions, *BMC Res. Notes* 9 (2016) 444.
- [48] C. Wang, C.J. Zhang, B.N. Martin, K. Bulek, Z. Kang, J. Zhao, G. Bian, J.A. Carman, J. Gao, A. Dongre, H. Xue, S.D. Miller, Y. Qian, D. Hambardzumyan, T. Hamilton, R.M. Ransohoff, X. Li, IL-17 induced NOTCH1 activation in oligodendrocyte progenitor cells enhances proliferation and inflammatory gene expression, *Nat. Commun.* 8 (2017), 15508.
- [49] Z. Kang, C. Wang, J. Zepp, L. Wu, K. Sun, J. Zhao, U. Chandrasekharan, P. E. DiCorleto, B.D. Trapp, R.M. Ransohoff, X. Li, Act1 mediates IL-17-induced EAE pathogenesis selectively in NG2+ glial cells, *Nat. Neurosci.* 16 (2013) 1401–1408.
- [50] C. Agresti, D. 'Urso, G. Levi, Reversible inhibitory effects of interferon-gamma and tumour necrosis factor-alpha on oligodendroglial lineage cell proliferation and differentiation in vitro, *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 8 (1996) 1106–1116.
- [51] M.K. Paintlia, A.S. Paintlia, A.K. Singh, I. Singh, Synergistic activity of interleukin-17 and tumor necrosis factor-alpha enhances oxidative stress-mediated oligodendrocyte apoptosis, *J. Neurochem.* 116 (2011) 508–521.
- [52] S. Marques, A. Zeisel, S. Codeluppi, D. van Bruggen, A. Mendanha Falcao, L. Xiao, H. Li, M. Haring, H. Hochgerner, R.A. Romanov, D. Gyllborg, A.B. Munoz-Manchado, G. La Manno, P. Lonnerberg, E.M. Floriddia, F. Rezayee, P. Ernfors, E. Arenas, J. Hjerling-Lefler, T. Harkany, W.D. Richardson, S. Linnarsson, G. Castelo-Branco, Oligodendrocyte heterogeneity in the mouse juvenile and adult central nervous system, *Science* 352 (2016) 1326–1329.
- [53] A. Zeisel, H. Hochgerner, P. Lönnerberg, A. Johnsson, F. Memic, J. van der Zwan, M. Häring, E. Braun, L.E. Borm, G. La Manno, S. Codeluppi, A. Furlan, K. Lee, N. Skene, K.D. Harris, J. Hjerling-Lefler, E. Arenas, P. Ernfors, U. Marklund, S. Linnarsson, Molecular architecture of the mouse nervous system, *Cell* 174 (2018) 999–1014, e1022.
- [54] T. Zeis, L. Enz, N. Schaeren-Wiemers, The immunomodulatory oligodendrocyte, *Brain Res.* 1641 (2016) 139–148.
- [55] S. Moyon, A.L. Dubessy, M.S. Agrot, M. Trotter, J.K. Huang, L. Dauphinot, M. C. Potier, C. Kerninon, S. Melik Parsadaniantz, R.J.M. Franklin, C. Lubetzki, Demyelination causes adult CNS progenitors to revert to an immature state and express immune cues that support their migration, *J. Neurosci.* 35 (2015) 4–20.
- [56] G. Ramesh, S. Benge, B. Pahar, M.T. Philipp, A possible role for inflammation in mediating apoptosis of oligodendrocytes as induced by the Lyme disease spirochete *Borrelia burgdorferi*, *J. Neuroinflamm.* 9 (2012) 72.
- [57] M.P. Hosking, L. Liu, R.M. Ransohoff, T.E. Lane, A protective role for ELR+ chemokines during acute viral encephalomyelitis, *PLoS Pathog.* 5 (2009), e1000648.
- [58] B.S. Marro, J.J. Grist, T.E. Lane, Inducible expression of CXCL1 within the central nervous system amplifies viral-induced demyelination, *J. Immunol.* 196 (2016) 1855–1864.
- [59] M. Tani, M.E. Fuentes, J.W. Peterson, B.D. Trapp, S.K. Durham, J.K. Loy, R. Bravo, R.M. Ransohoff, S.A. Lira, Neutrophil infiltration, glial reaction, and neurological disease in transgenic mice expressing the chemokine N51/KC in oligodendrocytes, *J. Clin. Invest.* 98 (1996) 529–539.
- [60] B.T. Fife, G.B. Huffnagle, W.A. Kuziel, W.J. Karpus, CC chemokine receptor 2 is critical for induction of experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis, *J. Exp. Med.* 192 (2000) 899–905.
- [61] A. Mildner, M. Mack, H. Schmidt, W. Bruck, M. Djukic, M.D. Zabel, A. Hille, J. Priller, M. Prinz, CCR2+Ly-6Chi monocytes are crucial for the effector phase of autoimmunity in the central nervous system, *Brain* 132 (2009) 2487–2500.
- [62] M. Wennstrom, S. Janelidze, C. Bay-Richter, L. Minthon, L. Brundin, Pro-inflammatory cytokines reduce the proliferation of NG2 cells and increase shedding of NG2 in vivo and in vitro, *PLOS One* 9 (2014), e109387.
- [63] S. Zhang, Q. Wang, Q. Yang, H. Gu, Y. Yin, Y. Li, J. Hou, R. Chen, Q. Sun, Y. Sun, G. Hu, J. Zhou, NG2 glia regulate brain innate immunity via TGF-beta2/TGFBR2 axis, *BMC Med.* 17 (2019) 204.
- [64] L. Peferoen, M. Kipp, P. van der Valk, J.M. van Noort, S. Amor, Oligodendrocyte-microglia cross-talk in the central nervous system, *Immunology* 141 (2014) 302–313.
- [65] C.S. Moore, Q.L. Cui, N.M. Warsi, B.A. Durafourt, N. Zorko, D.R. Owen, J.P. Antel, A. Bar-Or, Direct and indirect effects of immune and central nervous system-resident cells on human oligodendrocyte progenitor cell differentiation, *J. Immunol.* 194 (2015) 761–772.
- [66] A.E.S. Watson, K. Goodkey, T. Footz, A. Voronova, Regulation of CNS precursor function by neuronal chemokines, *Neurosci. Lett.* 715 (2020), 134533.
- [67] Y. Zhang, K. Chen, S.A. Sloan, M.L. Bennett, A.R. Scholze, S. O'Keefe, H. P. Phatnani, P. Guarnieri, C. Caneda, N. Ruderisch, S. Deng, S.A. Liddelow, C. Zhang, R. Daneman, T. Maniatis, B.A. Barres, J.Q. Wu, An RNA-sequencing transcriptome and splicing database of glia, neurons, and vascular cells of the cerebral cortex, *J. Neurosci.* 34 (2014) 11929–11947.
- [68] J. Niu, H.H. Tsai, K.K. Hoi, N. Huang, G. Yu, K. Kim, S.E. Baranzini, L. Xiao, J. R. Chan, S.P.J. Fancy, Aberrant oligodendroglial-vascular interactions disrupt the blood-brain barrier, triggering CNS inflammation, *Nat. Neurosci.* 22 (2019) 709–718.
- [69] P.A. Bretscher, A two-step, two-signal model for the primary activation of precursor helper T cells, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 96 (1999) 185–190.
- [70] J.M. Curtissinger, C.S. Schmidt, A. Mondino, D.C. Lins, R.M. Kedl, M.K. Jenkins, M. F. Mescher, Inflammatory cytokines provide a third signal for activation of naive CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, *J. Immunol.* 162 (1999) 3256–3262.
- [71] C.A. Janeway Jr., K. Bottomly, Signals and signs for lymphocyte responses, *Cell* 76 (1994) 275–285.
- [72] H. Sepulveda, A. Cerwenka, T. Morgan, R.W. Dutton, CD28, IL-2-independent costimulatory pathways for CD8 T lymphocyte activation, *J. Immunol.* 163 (1999) 1133–1142.
- [73] A. Fernández-Castañeda, M.S. Chappell, D.A. Rosen, S.M. Seki, R.M. Beiter, D. M. Johanson, D. Liskey, E. Farber, S. Onengut-Gumuscuk, C.C. Overall, J.L. Dupree, A. Gaultier, The active contribution of OPCs to neuroinflammation is mediated by LRPI, *Acta Neuropathol.* 139 (2020) 365–382.
- [74] S. Hisahara, Targeted expression of baculovirus p35 caspase inhibitor in oligodendrocytes protects mice against autoimmune-mediated demyelination, *EMBO J.* 19 (2000) 341–348.
- [75] S. Hisahara, J. Yuan, T. Momoi, H. Okano, M. Miura, Caspase-11 mediates oligodendrocyte cell death and pathogenesis of autoimmune-mediated demyelination, *J. Exp. Med.* 193 (2001) 111–122.
- [76] A.V. Capriariello, J.A. Rogers, M.L. Morgan, V. Hoghooghi, J.R. Plemel, A. Koebel, S. Tsutsui, J.F. Dunn, L.P. Kotra, S.S. Ousman, V. Wee Yong, P.K. Stys, Biochemically altered myelin triggers autoimmune demyelination, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 115 (2018) 5528–5533.
- [77] M. Traka, J.R. Podojil, D.P. McCarthy, S.D. Miller, B. Popko, Oligodendrocyte death results in immune-mediated CNS demyelination, *Nat. Neurosci.* 19 (2016) 65–74.
- [78] G. Locatelli, S. Wörtge, T. Buch, B. Ingold, F. Frommer, B. Sobottka, M. Krüger, K. Karram, C. Bühlmann, I. Bechmann, F.L. Heppner, A. Waisman, B. Becher, Primary oligodendrocyte death does not elicit anti-CNS immunity, *Nat. Neurosci.* 15 (2012) 543–550.
- [79] P.H. Larsen, J.E. Wells, W.B. Stallcup, G. Opendakker, V.W. Yong, Matrix metalloproteinase-9 facilitates remyelination in part by processing the inhibitory NG2 proteoglycan, *J. Neurosci.* 23 (2003) 11127–11135.
- [80] P.H. Larsen, V.W. Yong, The expression of matrix metalloproteinase-12 by oligodendrocytes regulates their maturation and morphological differentiation, *J. Neurosci.* 24 (2004) 7597–7603.
- [81] J. Palazuelos, H.C. Crawford, M. Klingener, B. Sun, J. Karelis, E.W. Raines, A. Aguirre, TACE/ADAM17 is essential for oligodendrocyte development and CNS myelination, *J. Neurosci.* 34 (2014) 11884–11896.
- [82] Y. Dombrowski, T. O'Hagan, M. Dittmer, R. Penalba, S.R. Mayoral, P. Bankhead, S. Fleville, G. Eleftheriadis, C. Zhao, M. Naughton, R. Hassan, J. Moffat, J. Falconer, A. Boyd, P. Hamilton, I.V. Allen, A. Kissenpfennig, P.N. Moynagh, E. Evergren, B. Perbal, A.C. Williams, R.J. Ingram, J.R. Chan, R.J.M. Franklin, D. C. Fitzgerald, Regulatory T cells promote myelin regeneration in the central nervous system, *Nat. Neurosci.* 20 (2017) 674–680.
- [83] A. Pennati, E.A. Nylén, I.D. Duncan, J. Galipeau, Regulatory B cells normalize CNS myeloid cell content in a mouse model of multiple sclerosis and promote oligodendrogenesis and remyelination, *J. Neurosci.* 40 (2020) 5105–5115.
- [84] S. Jäkel, E. Agirre, A.M. Falcão, D. van Bruggen, K.W. Lee, I. Kuesel, D. Malhotra, C. ffrench-Constant, A. Williams, G. Castelo-Branco, Altered human oligodendrocyte heterogeneity in multiple sclerosis, *Nature* 566 (2019) 543–547.
- [85] L. Schirmer, D. Velmeshev, S. Holmqvist, M. Kaufmann, S. Werneburg, D. Jung, S. Vistnes, J.H. Stockley, A. Young, M. Steindel, B. Tung, N. Goyal, A. Bhaduri, S. Mayer, J.B. Engler, O.A. Bayraktar, R.J.M. Franklin, M. Haussler, R. Reynolds, D.P. Schafer, M.A. Friese, L.R. Shioh, A.R. Kriegstein, D.H. Rowitch, Neuronal vulnerability and multilineage diversity in multiple sclerosis, *Nature* 573 (2019) 75–82.
- [86] Y. Zhou, W.M. Song, P.S. Andhey, A. Swain, T. Levy, K.R. Miller, P.L. Poliani, M. Cominelli, S. Grover, S. Gilfillan, M. Cella, T.K. Ulland, K. Zaitsev, A. Miyashita, T. Ikeuchi, M. Sainouchi, A. Kakita, D.A. Bennett, J.A. Schneider, M.R. Nichols, S. A. Beausoleil, J.D. Ulrich, D.M. Holtzman, M.N. Artyomov, M. Colonna, Human and mouse single-nucleus transcriptomics reveal TREM2-dependent and TREM2-independent cellular responses in Alzheimer's disease, *Nat. Med.* 26 (2020) 131–142.
- [87] M. Ximerakis, S.L. Lipnick, B.T. Innes, S.K. Simmons, X. Adiconis, D. Dionne, B. A. Mayweather, L. Nguyen, Z. Niziolek, C. Ozek, V.L. Butty, R. Isserlin, S. M. Buchanan, S.S. Levine, A. Regev, G.D. Bader, J.Z. Levin, L.L. Rubin, Single-cell transcriptomic profiling of the aging mouse brain, *Nat. Neurosci.* 22 (2019) 1696–1708.
- [88] S.O. Spitzer, S. Sitnikov, Y. Kamen, K.A. Evans, D. Kronenberg-Versteeg, S. Dietmann, O. de Faria Jr., S. Agathou, R.T. Karadottir, Oligodendrocyte Progenitor Cells Become Regionally Diverse and Heterogeneous with Age, *Neuron* 101 (2019) 459–471, e455.
- [89] B.W. Dulken, M.T. Buckley, P. Navarro Negro, N. Saligrama, R. Cayrol, D. S. Leeman, B.M. George, S.C. Boutet, K. Hebestreit, J.V. Pluvinage, T. Wyss-Coray, I.L. Weissman, H. Vogel, M.M. Davis, A. Brunet, Single-cell analysis reveals T cell infiltration in old neurogenic niches, *Nature* 571 (2019) 205–210.
- [90] A. Giladi, L.K. Wagner, H. Li, D. Dörr, C. Medaglia, F. Paul, A. Shemer, S. Jung, S. Yona, M. Mack, A. Leutz, I. Amit, A. Mildner, A. Giladi, L.K. Wagner, H. Li, D. Dörr, C. Medaglia, F. Paul, A. Shemer, S. Jung, S. Yona, M. Mack, A. Leutz, I. Amit, A. Mildner, Cxcl10+

- monocytes define a pathogenic subset in the central nervous system during autoimmune neuroinflammation, *Nat. Immunol.* 21 (2020) 962.
- [91] M.J.C. Jordão, R. Sankowski, S.M. Brendecke, Sagar, G. Locatelli, Y.H. Tai, T. L. Tay, E. Schramm, S. Armbruster, N. Hagemeyer, O. Groß, D. Mai, Ö. Çiçek, T. Falk, M. Kerschensteiner, D. Grün, M. Prinz, Single-cell profiling identifies myeloid cell subsets with distinct fates during neuroinflammation, *Science* 363 (2019), eaat7554.
- [92] T. Masuda, R. Sankowski, O. Staszewski, C. Böttcher, L. Amann, Sagar, C. Scheiwe, S. Nessler, P. Kunz, G. van Loo, V.A. Coenen, P.C. Reinacher, A. Michel, U. Sure, R. Gold, D. Grün, J. Priller, C. Stadelmann, M. Prinz, Spatial and temporal heterogeneity of mouse and human microglia at single-cell resolution, *Nature* 566 (2019) 388–392.
- [93] C. International Multiple Sclerosis Genetics, Multiple sclerosis genomic map implicates peripheral immune cells and microglia in susceptibility, *Science* 365 (2019), eaav7188.
- [94] D.C. Factor, A.M. Barbeau, K.C. Allan, L.R. Hu, M. Madhavan, A.T. Hoang, K.E. A. Hazel, P.A. Hall, S. Nisraiyya, F.J. Najm, T.E. Miller, Z.S. Nevin, R.T. Karl, B. R. Lima, Y. Song, A.G. Sibert, G.K. Dhillon, C. Volsko, C.F. Bartels, D.J. Adams, R. Dutta, M.D. Gallagher, W. Phu, A. Kozlenkov, S. Dracheva, P.C. Scacheri, P. J. Tesar, O. Corradin, Cell type-specific intralocus interactions reveal oligodendrocyte mechanisms in MS, *Cell* 181 (2020) 382–395, e321.
- [95] I.E. Morales Pantoja, M.D. Smith, L. Rajbhandari, L. Cheng, Y. Gao, V. Mahairaki, A. Venkatesan, P.A. Calabresi, K.C. Fitzgerald, K.A. Whartenby, iPSCs from people with MS can differentiate into oligodendrocytes in a homeostatic but not an inflammatory milieu, *PLOS One* 15 (2020), e0233980.
- [96] L. Starost, M. Lindner, M. Herold, Y.K.T. Xu, H.C.A. Drexler, K. Heß, M. Ehrlich, L. Ottoboni, F. Ruffini, M. Stehling, A. Röpke, C. Thomas, H.R. Schöler, J. Antel, J. Winkler, G. Martino, L. Klotz, T. Kuhlmann, Extrinsic immune cell-derived, but not intrinsic oligodendroglial factors contribute to oligodendroglial differentiation block in multiple sclerosis, *Acta Neuropathol.* 140 (2020) 715–736.
- [97] M.S. Windrem, M. Osipovitch, Z. Liu, J. Bates, D. Chandler-Militello, L. Zou, J. Munir, S. Schanz, K. McCoy, R.H. Miller, S. Wang, M. Nedergaard, R.L. Findling, P.J. Tesar, S.A. Goldman, Human iPSC glial mouse chimeras reveal glial contributions to schizophrenia, *Cell Stem Cell* 21 (2017) 195–208, e196.
- [98] M. Meijer, E. Agirre, M. Kabbe, C.A. van Tuijn, A. Heskol, A.M. Falcão, M. R. Corces, T.J. Montine, X. Chen, H.Y. Chang, et al., A primed immune transcriptional program is activated in oligodendroglia in multiple sclerosis, *bioRxiv* (2020), 2020.2007.2021.213876.